

1 **Quantifying exposure of wild bumblebees to mixtures of agrochemicals in agricultural and**
2 **urban landscapes**

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10 **Abstract**

11 The increased use of pesticides has caused concern over the possible direct association of
12 exposure to combinations of these compounds with bee health problems. There is growing
13 proof that bees are regularly exposed to mixtures of agrochemicals, but most research has
14 been focused on managed bees living in farmland, whereas little is known about exposure of
15 wild bees, both in farmland and urban habitats. To determine exposure of wild bumblebees to
16 pesticides in agricultural and urban environments through the season, specimens of five
17 different species were collected from farms and ornamental urban gardens in three sampling
18 periods. Five neonicotinoid insecticides, thirteen fungicides and a pesticide synergist were
19 analysed in each of the specimens collected. In total, 61% of the 150 individuals tested had
20 detectable levels of at least one of the compounds, with boscalid being the most frequently
21 detected (35%), followed by tebuconazole (27%), spiroxamine (19%), carbendazim (11%),
22 epoxiconazole (8%), imidacloprid (7%), metconazole (7%) and thiamethoxam (6%).
23 Quantifiable concentrations ranged from 0.17 to 54.4 ng/g (bee body weight) for individual
24 pesticides. From all the bees where pesticides were detected, the majority (71%) had more
25 than one compound, with a maximum of seven pesticides detected in one specimen.
26 Concentrations and detection frequencies were higher in bees collected from farmland
27 compared to urban sites, and pesticide concentrations decreased through the season. Overall,
28 our results show that wild bumblebees are exposed to multiple pesticides when foraging in
29 agricultural and urban landscapes. Such mixtures are detected in bee tissues not just during
30 the crop flowering period, but also later in the season. Therefore, contact with these
31 combinations of active compounds might be more prolonged in time and widespread in the
32 environment than previously assumed. These findings may help to direct future research and
33 pesticide regulation strategies to promote the conservation of wild bee populations.

34 **Main findings:** There is a widespread presence of multiple pesticide residues in free-flying wild
35 bumblebees, with different levels and frequencies of detection according to the species,
36 sampling period and landscape context.

37 **Keywords:** neonicotinoids; fungicides; pesticide mixtures; wild bumblebees; pesticide
38 exposure

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Bees are exposed to environmental pollutants via contaminated food resources such as pollen,
41 nectar or water (Bonmatin et al., 2015), and through external contact with aerosols during
42 spraying and contaminated dust emitted during the sowing of dressed seeds as their hairy
43 bodies trap particulate residues (Greig-Smith et al., 1994; Pistorius et al., 2015). Many studies
44 have used honeybees as relevant organisms to monitor environmental pollution (Celli and
45 Maccagnani, 2003; Porrini et al., 2003). Bumblebees also forage in a great diversity of places
46 and strongly interact with the environment, mainly the flora, surrounding their nests in a range
47 of maximum foraging distances of 363 to 1650 m depending on the species (Walther-Hellwig
48 and Frankl, 2000; Wood et al., 2015), and are thus also suitable organisms for monitoring
49 landscape-based ecological pollution.

50 While most pesticide research has been focused on managed bees, there has been less work
51 on wild bee populations. For instance, the only European bumblebee that has been studied in
52 relation to pesticide exposure and toxicology is *Bombus terrestris*, simply because this species
53 is easy to rear in captivity and commercially reared colonies are readily available (Baron et al.,
54 2014; Gill et al., 2012; Rundlöf et al., 2015; Whitehorn et al., 2012).

55 There is increasing evidence that managed bees living in agricultural landscapes are routinely
56 exposed to mixtures of agrochemicals (David et al., 2016; Lambert et al., 2013; Long and
57 Krupke, 2016; Mullin et al., 2010; Pettis et al., 2013), but little is known about the exposure of
58 wild bees in these environments (Hladik et al., 2016). Nevertheless, bees constitute a highly
59 diverse group where different taxonomic groups differ widely in their vulnerability to pesticide
60 exposure (Biddinger et al., 2013; Devillers et al., 2007; Piironen and Goulson, 2016; Thompson
61 and Hunt, 1999). Furthermore, bee species exhibit pronounced differences in floral
62 preferences and foraging habits, collecting pollen and nectar more frequently from particular
63 plant species according to their morphological traits (e.g. tongue length, body shape and size)
64 and nutritional needs (Goulson et al., 2008; Vanderplanck et al., 2014; Vaudo et al., 2016).
65 Such foraging choices may profoundly influence the probability of bees to be more or less

66 exposed to some active compounds (Woodcock et al., 2016). Treated crop plants growing in
67 agricultural landscapes have often been regarded as the only source of exposure to
68 agrochemicals for pollinators, but recent research revealed their presence in wild plants
69 growing near crops (Botías et al., 2015; David et al., 2016; Long and Krupke, 2016; Mogren and
70 Lundgren, 2016). We would expect bees that visit flowering arable crops to have higher
71 exposure than those that do not, but also those that visit wild plant species may have varying
72 exposure depending on the ecology, physiology and morphology of their preferred flowers
73 (Botías et al., 2016). Therefore, it is essential to understand the possible differences in levels of
74 exposure among bee species, since this could reveal which are the most likely exposed and the
75 most frequent mixtures of agrochemicals that they are exposed to.

76 The widespread occurrence of mixtures of agrochemicals in bee tissues (Hladik et al., 2016)
77 increases concerns regarding the possible detrimental effects of simultaneous exposure to a
78 cocktail of compounds. In general, only the effects of single active substances are studied in
79 toxicity studies both for research and pesticide registration protocols, and exposure to
80 mixtures are only evaluated in risks assessments when they are part of the same formulation.
81 However, the application of two or more plant protection products during the same cropping
82 season is a common practice in conventional farming (Botías et al., 2015; Garthwaite et al.,
83 2013), and hence complex mixtures of agrochemicals which are not co-formulants of a single
84 product can be simultaneously detected in bee forage and bee tissues (David et al., 2016;
85 Hladik et al., 2016; Long and Krupke, 2016). This issue is worrisome given that exposure to
86 mixtures might pose higher risks for animal health than the single impact of a specific class of
87 compounds (Cedergreen, 2014; Rizzati et al., 2016). For example, some combinations of
88 insecticides (*e.g.* pyrethroids with neonicotinoids) and of insecticides with fungicides can lead
89 to additive and synergistic toxicity for bees at the individual and the colony level (Gill et al.,
90 2012; Iwasa et al., 2004; Schmuck et al., 2003; Sgolastra et al., 2016). The scarcity of
91 information on the field-relevant mixtures of agrochemicals and levels of exposure for bees
92 could lead us to overlook the possible additive or synergistic effects of pesticide mixtures when
93 risk assessment studies are performed, some of which have been designed to evaluate the
94 hazards of such combinations (Sánchez-Bayo and Goka, 2014).

95 Another major gap in knowledge regarding exposure of bees to pesticides is the potential
96 uptake and contact with these compounds in urban areas, where ornamental nursery plants
97 can also be treated with pesticides (Brown et al., 2013; Fevery et al., 2016) and no information
98 is available on their use in domestic gardens. The possible exposure of bees to harmful

99 pesticides through forage collected in gardens is of high ecological concern, since these
100 habitats are of great value for bees, providing nectar, pollen and nest sites, and sustaining a
101 remarkably high pollinator species richness and abundance (Baldock et al., 2015; Kaluza et al.,
102 2016; Samnegård et al., 2011), including bumblebees (Fetridge et al., 2008; Goulson et al.,
103 2010). If foraging resources and nesting sites in urban habitats are contaminated with
104 pesticide residues, it is likely that exposure to certain active compounds could be more widely
105 spread in the landscape and more prolonged in time than previously assumed.

106 The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare exposure in different wild bumblebee
107 species. To do this, we analysed the levels of five neonicotinoid insecticides, thirteen currently-
108 used fungicides and a pesticide synergist in tissues of five bumblebee species (*B. hortorum*, *B.*
109 *pasuorum*, *B. terrestris*, *B. lapidarius* and *B. pratorum*). These wild bumblebee samples were
110 collected in agricultural and urban habitats to compare levels of exposure in both
111 environments and to study distribution of agrochemicals in the landscape. The bees were
112 gathered in three different periods (late spring, early summer and midsummer) in order to
113 monitor the length of exposure to agrochemicals through the season.

114 Our results show evidence that wild bumblebees are frequently exposed to mixtures of
115 agrochemicals when they forage in arable and urban habitats, with peak concentrations
116 decreasing through the season.

117 **2. Materials and Methods**

118 **2.1. Sampling sites and field collection**

119 Wild bumblebees were collected in five farms and five urban landscapes in East Sussex (South-
120 East England, UK), all sites being at least 2 kilometers apart from each other (Figure 1) (Table
121 S1). The sites selected to collect bees in agricultural land consisted of arable fields within
122 mixed farms, where the predominant crops were oilseed rape, winter wheat and spring barley,
123 and part of the land was pasture. The urban sampling sites consisted of ornamental public
124 gardens and parks surrounded by houses that had private gardens in most cases. Foraging
125 bumblebees were collected using insect nets and kept in individual labeled tubes and put on
126 ice during transport back to the lab, and then kept at -80°C until pesticide analysis was
127 performed. Specimens of five bumblebee species with different ranges of tongue length were
128 sampled (Brodie, 1996; Prys-Jones and Corbet, 2011): short-tongued bumblebees were *B.*
129 *pratorum* (6.4 - 7.1 mm), *B. lapidarius* (6 - 8.1 mm), *B. terrestris* (5.8 - 8.2 mm); medium-
130 tongued was *B. pasuorum* (7.6 - 8.6 mm); and long-tongued was *B. hortorum* (12 - 13.5 mm)

131 (Table 1). The flowers where the bees were foraging at the time of capture were recorded
132 (Tables S2a-S1c), since bumblebees exhibit a high degree of floral constancy (Wilson and Stine,
133 1996), and this may help predict exposure.

134 Bumblebee individuals were gathered during three sampling periods, spring (27/04/14 –
135 14/05/14), early summer (5/06/14 – 23/06/14) and midsummer (15/07/14 – 2/08/14), and 150
136 bee individuals were collected in total. Oilseed rape crops were in bloom during the first
137 sampling period (late spring), and 18 out of the 25 individuals gathered in arable sites during
138 that period were foraging in oilseed rape crops when collected (Table S2a). The pesticide usage
139 information of the crops where bees were foraging was not provided by the farmers. The EU
140 moratorium on the use of neonicotinoid insecticides started on the 1st December 2013, but the
141 oilseed rape crops that were in bloom in the 2014 spring were sown at the end of August-
142 beginning of September 2013, so these crops were still allowed to be seed-treated with
143 neonicotinoids.

144 **2.2. Pesticide analysis**

145 *Chemicals and reagents*

146 Eight classes of contaminants were chosen to be tested in the bumblebee samples, including
147 the five neonicotinoid insecticides that are registered for use in the UK, based on the most
148 used (by weight or area treated) in UK crops including oilseed rape, wheat, spring barley, field
149 bean, strawberry and raspberry crops
150 (<https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/pusstats/surveys/2014surveys.cfm>) (Table S3). Except for
151 certified standards of carbendazim-d3 and tebuconazole-d6, which were purchased from LGC
152 standards UK and carbamazepine-d10 and prochloraz-d7 from QMX Laboratories Limited UK,
153 all the other certified standards as well as formic acid, magnesium sulphate, ammonium
154 formate, sodium acetate and SupelTM QuE PSA/C18/GCB (ratio 1/1/1) were obtained from
155 Sigma Aldrich UK. The compound purity of the pesticide standards was > 99%, apart from
156 spiroxamine (98.5%), triticonazole (98.8%), piperonyl butoxide (97.9%). Isotopic purity of
157 deuterated standards was > 97%. HPLC grade acetonitrile, toluene and water were obtained
158 from Rathburns UK.

159 *Preparation of samples and residue analysis*

160 The extraction of pesticides from the bumblebee samples was performed as reported in David
161 et al., 2015.

162 Briefly, individual whole bumblebee specimens (N = 150) were ground in liquid nitrogen and
163 weighed (mean weight \pm S.D = 108 \pm 46 mg; range = 21 – 236 mg). Each sample was spiked
164 with 10 μ l acetonitrile containing the mixture of deuterated internal standards (IS) at 40 ng/ml
165 (400 pg of each IS). Subsequently, the extraction was performed by the addition of 400 μ l of
166 water, 500 μ l of acetonitrile, 250 mg of magnesium sulphate: sodium acetate mix (4:1) and 50
167 mg of SupelTM QuE PSA/C18/GCB for the dispersive solid phase extraction step (dSPE)
168 (QuEChERS method). After the dSPE step, the sorbent was extracted with acetonitrile/toluene
169 (3/1, 150 μ l) and the supernatant was combined with that of the previous acetonitrile extract
170 and spin filtered (0.22 μ m). After evaporation, reconstitution was made with 120 μ l
171 acetonitrile:water (30:70) and the extract was centrifuged (20 min). The supernatant obtained
172 was stored in the dark at -20°C before analysis.

173 *UHPLC-MS/MS analyses*

174 Extracts of samples were analysed by ultra high-performance liquid chromatography tandem
175 mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) as described in David et al. (2015), using a Waters Acquity
176 UHPLC system coupled to a Quattro Premier triple quadrupole mass spectrometer from
177 Micromass (Waters, Manchester, UK). Acquisition of data was performed with the software
178 MassLynx 4.1 and the quantification was established by the calculation of the response factor
179 of each pesticide to its internal standard. Least-square linear regression analysis of the native
180 analyte to deuterated internal standard (concentration ratio) versus the peak area was used to
181 determine analyte concentrations. Further methodological details are described in David et al.
182 (2015).

183 Table S4 reports the method detection limits (MDL) and the method quantification limits
184 (MQL) for all the compounds that were analysed in bumblebees.

185 **2.3. Statistical analysis**

186 Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess whether data (i.e. concentration of pesticides detected in
187 the bumblebees per species, habitat, sampling period and bumblebee body mass) met the
188 assumptions of normality. Since pesticide concentrations did not meet the assumptions of
189 normality, non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare this variable among the
190 5 different bee species and 3 sampling periods. Pairwise comparisons between bee species,
191 sampling periods and habitats were performed using Mann–Whitney U-tests. Bumblebee body
192 mass and frequencies of pesticide detection in the 5 species were normally distributed, so one-
193 way ANOVA analyses were carried out to compare weights of the 5 species, using Bonferroni

194 post-hoc tests for pairwise comparisons, and to compare the frequencies of detection among
195 them. For the statistical analysis, the MDL value was assigned to concentrations above the
196 limits of detection (\geq MDL) but below the limits of quantification ($>$ MQL), whereas those below
197 the MDL were considered to be zero. The software used to perform the statistical analysis was
198 SPSS 21.

199 **3. Results**

200 *Ranges, frequencies and average levels of neonicotinoid and fungicide residues detected in wild* 201 *bumblebee samples*

202 In total, 60.7% of the 150 individuals tested had detectable levels of at least one of the
203 compounds analysed, with boscalid being the most frequently detected (in 35.3 % of all the
204 bees analysed), followed by tebuconazole (27.3%), spiroxamine (18.7%), carbendazim (10.7%),
205 epoxiconazole (8%), imidacloprid (7.3%), metconazole (6.7%) and thiamethoxam (6%) (Table 2)
206 (Tables S2a-2c). In general, from all the bees where pesticides were detected, the majority
207 (71.4%) had more than one compound, and 43.4 % of the bees contained two or more, with a
208 maximum of 7 different pesticides being detected in one specimen (*B. lapidarius* collected
209 from urban site 2 in June) (Table S2b).

210 *Levels of pesticide exposure for the five bumblebee species studied*

211 Although the combinations of pesticides detected varied notably among individuals of the
212 same and the other species, some combinations occurred very frequently in farmland
213 bumblebees. Boscalid with DMI-fungicides was the most common mixture detected in
214 bumblebees (64%) foraging in farmland in spring (April-May), except for *B. pratorum*
215 individuals where such combination was not detected (Table S2a). In early summer (June)
216 spiroxamine with DMI-fungicides was detected in the great majority of farmland bumblebees
217 (88%), regardless of the species (Table S2b) (Figures 2 and 3). In general, the detection
218 frequency of the 19 agrochemicals analysed did not significantly differ among the 5 species
219 (ANOVA, $F(4, 25) = 0.78$, $P = 0.55$). However, when the concentrations of pesticides detected
220 in the 5 bumblebee species were compared, we found that *B. pratorum*, the species with the
221 lowest body mass and shortest tongue length range (Table 1), had significantly lower residue
222 levels (mean \pm SD = 1.7 ± 3.6 ng/g) than *B. hortorum* (4.7 ± 10.1 ng/g) (M-W test: $U(58) = 291$;
223 $P = 0.013$), *B. terrestris* (6.8 ± 10.4 ng/g) ($U(58) = 275$; $P = 0.006$), *B. lapidarius* (7.2 ± 11.8)
224 ($U(58) = 260$; $P = 0.003$) and also tended to have lower concentrations than *B. pascuorum* (2.8
225 ± 4.9) ($U(58) = 330$; $P = 0.056$).

226 In order to evaluate the relationship between bee body size and levels of exposure, we
227 compared the body mass of the five bumblebee species, and we found that *B. pratorum* was
228 significantly lighter than the two species with the highest pesticide concentrations, *B. terrestris*
229 (1-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison test: $P = 0.03$) and *B. lapidarius* ($P =$
230 0.017).

231 *Levels of pesticide exposure in arable and urban habitats*

232 In general, bees foraging in agricultural landscapes had significantly higher levels of
233 agrochemicals (6.8 ± 9.5 ng/g) than those foraging in urban sites (2.5 ± 7.8 ng/g)(M-W test:
234 $U(148) = 1635.5$; $Z = -4.6$; $P < 0.001$)(Figure 2). However, the highest levels and frequencies of
235 detection for neonicotinoids (10 ng/g of imidacloprid on a *B. terrestris* specimen) and the most
236 frequently detected fungicide boscalid (54.5 ng/g in a *B. lapidarius* specimen) were recorded in
237 urban bumblebees collected during the early summer (June) (Table S2b). Overall,
238 neonicotinoids were found in more bees in urban sites than in farmland (9.3% versus 2.7%),
239 with all five neonicotinoids registered for use in the UK found in at least one urban bee.

240 *Changing levels of pesticide exposure through the season*

241 The levels of exposure to agrochemicals for wild bumblebees were examined for the period of
242 highest foraging activity in the studied area (East Sussex, England), and we found that the
243 frequencies of detection decreased both in arable and urban habitats for the 5 species
244 evaluated in midsummer (July) (Figure 3), when only 28% of the bees collected had at least
245 one agrochemical, compared to 76% in late spring (April-May) and 78% in early summer (June).
246 Consequently, the average concentrations detected were lower in midsummer (July: 0.6 ± 2.3
247 ng/g) than in spring (April-May: 5.9 ± 7.6 ng/g) (M-W test: $U(98) = 474$; $Z = -5.67$; $P < 0.001$)
248 and early summer (June: 7.5 ± 12.4 ng/g) (M-W test: $U(98) = 462.5$; $Z = -5.74$; $P < 0.001$) (Table
249 2).

250 **4. Discussion**

251 Our field study revealed that free-flying wild bumblebees are exposed to multiple pesticide
252 residues, with different levels and frequencies of detection according to the species, sampling
253 period and landscape context. Several studies have reported the presence of mixtures of
254 agrochemicals in honeybee matrices (Lambert et al., 2013; Mullin et al., 2010; Pettis et al.,
255 2013), where more than 170 compounds have been detected so far (Sánchez-Bayo and Goka,
256 2014), but little is known about the exposure of wild bees. Recent research detected up to 19

257 different chemicals in native bees collected from wheat fields and grassland in Colorado (USA)
258 (Hladik et al., 2016), reporting levels as high as 310 ng/g for thiamethoxam, 87 ng/g for
259 clothianidin and 82 ng/g for imidacloprid. The maximum concentrations detected in our
260 bumblebee samples were much lower (i.e. 2.35 ng/g for thiamethoxam, 1.4 ng/g for
261 clothianidin and 10 ng/g for imidacloprid), which could be explained by the differences
262 between both experimental designs. While we collected free-flying bumblebees with nets and
263 analysed them individually, Hladik et al. (2016) performed the analysis on composite samples
264 containing approximately 10 individuals of different wild bee species that were collected using
265 bee monitoring traps. The collection and analysis of composite samples containing individuals
266 from different bee genera might conceivably increase the chances of including particular
267 specimens that could have been exposed to very high concentrations of pesticides due to their
268 foraging and feeding behaviour, metabolic rates and morphological traits. Although the
269 bumblebee species analysed in our study can present differences in their foraging distances,
270 they seem to use and benefit similarly from the resources available in farmland (Wood et al.,
271 2015), while bees from other genera, specially solitary bees, may present more variation in
272 their foraging choices (Wood et al., 2016), and thus, a wider range of levels of exposure to
273 agrochemicals. On the other hand, the dissimilarities in pesticide use patterns between the UK
274 and the USA could partly explain the differences found, as for instance, the maximum
275 application rate for thiamethoxam in oil seed crops in the UK is 33.6 g a.i./ha (European Food
276 Safety Authority, 2013), and 157 g a.i./ha in the USA (USEPA, 2011). Studying the link between
277 pesticide application rates and the levels of exposure for bees, and how different bee species
278 can be more or less susceptible to exposure is essential for a full understanding of the risk
279 posed by pesticides.

280 The comparison of pesticide concentrations among the five bumblebee species that we
281 studied showed that *B. pratorum*, the species with the smallest body mass and tongue length
282 range, had lower residue levels than the other four species. Different explanations are
283 plausible; for example smaller bees may consume lower amounts of food, and hence they
284 would be less exposed to these active compounds present in pollen and nectar. Smaller body
285 size may lead to greater mass-specific metabolic rates (Heinrich, 1993), and so pesticides might
286 be metabolised faster in smaller bees such as *B. pratorum*, whose body mass was significantly
287 lower than that of the two species with the highest pesticide concentrations, *B. terrestris* and
288 *B. lapidarius*.

289 Neonicotinoid insecticides can be metabolised relatively fast, with metabolites being the main
290 residues detected in bees a few minutes after ingestion of the parent compound (Brunet et al.,
291 2005; Suchail et al., 2004). Also the metabolites of some fungicides have been detected in bees
292 and bee-collected pollen (Jabot et al., 2016; Mullin et al., 2010; Stoner and Eitzer, 2013), so the
293 analysis of neonicotinoid and fungicide metabolites could have revealed the presence of other
294 potentially toxic compounds that bees might have been exposed to. Some neonicotinoid
295 metabolites have been proven to be highly toxic for bees (Simon-Delso et al., 2015; Suchail et
296 al., 2004, 2001), while the possible effects of both parent fungicides and their metabolites has
297 been scarcely studied in bees, with some reports showing detrimental effects (Bernauer et al.,
298 2015; Pettis et al., 2013; Syromyatnikov et al., 2016; vanEngelsdorp et al., 2009). It is possible
299 that the action of fungicides on bees may not be directly toxic, as is the case with insecticides,
300 but may alter the beneficial microbiome present in the pollen and nectar (Bartlewicz et al.,
301 2016; vanEngelsdorp et al., 2009; Yoder et al., 2013) and as a consequence, in the bee gut,
302 which could have important implications for bee nutrition and health (Engel et al., 2016;
303 Mattila et al., 2012; Pettis et al., 2013).

304 The tongue length of the different bumblebee species could be hypothesized as a possible
305 predictor of residue exposure, since this trait determines whether or not, and how fast, a bee
306 can manipulate a particular flower to extract nectar, and thus it is crucial for the division of
307 resources between different species (Brian, 2016; Cariveau et al., 2016; Goulson et al., 2008;
308 Harder, 2013). Long-tongued bees generally forage from long-corolla flowers, and short-
309 tongued bees from short corolla flowers (Hobbs, 1962). In the case of *B. pratorum*, as a short-
310 tongued bee, the most commonly visited flowers should be those with short corolla (*e.g.* many
311 Rosaceae and Asteraceae flowers), which have both nectaries and stamens more exposed to
312 environmental conditions and wind-blown aerosols. Oilseed rape flowers are shallow and
313 more frequently visited by short-tongued bees, even though the long-tongued bumblebee *B.*
314 *hortorum* often collects pollen from this plant (Stanley et al., 2013), and all our *B. hortorum*
315 specimens sampled in farmland in late spring were foraging in these crop flowers when
316 collected (Table S2a). Some of the pesticides analysed in this study have been reported to
317 degrade after exposure to sun light and/or high temperatures (*i.e.* some neonicotinoids,
318 carbendazim, carboxin, epoxiconazole and prochloraz) (Bonmatin et al., 2015; Burrows et al.,
319 2002; Mazellier et al., 2002), so it is possible that the flowers with pollen and nectar more
320 exposed to the environmental conditions might have lower concentrations of the parent active
321 compounds. Therefore, the bees feeding on these shallow flowers would be less exposed to
322 them. However, the tongue length range of *B. pratorum* is not very different to that of the

323 short-tongued bumblebees *B. terrestris* and *B. lapidarius* (Table 1). Moreover, the range of
324 flowers visited by the three species did not differ remarkably, since more than half (53%) of
325 the plant species visited by *B. terrestris* and *B. lapidarius* were also visited by *B. pratorum* in
326 May and June (*i.e.* when concentrations detected were higher) (Tables S2a-2b). Nevertheless,
327 as mentioned above, *B. terrestris* and *B. lapidarius* showed significantly higher levels of
328 pesticide concentrations than *B. pratorum*, so the tongue length doesn't seem to be a suitable
329 predictor of residue exposure for the group of bumblebees species studied here. Otherwise, a
330 bigger sample size might be needed to test this hypothesis.

331 Regarding the toxicity of the pesticides detected, it is worth noting that the bumblebee
332 specimens collected in the present study were individually processed as whole samples to
333 include residues on external as well as internal parts of the bees, so it is not possible to
334 differentiate if the pesticides detected were on the cuticle (contact toxicity) or inside the
335 organism (oral). Thus, both routes of exposure should be considered when the levels detected
336 in the samples are compared to lethal doses reported for the compounds analysed. Moreover,
337 as the bee gut was not removed before processing the samples, there is a chance that some of
338 the residues detected were present in the nectar and pollen contained in the digestive tract,
339 although we consider that the bulk of the bee weights were formed by bee tissues. None of
340 the residues detected in bumblebees were found to overlap with contact or oral acute LD₅₀
341 values tested on bumblebees or honeybees (Table 2), which is to be expected since the bees
342 screened for pesticides in this study were performing foraging tasks and appeared to be
343 healthy at the time of collection; it would be very unlikely to catch bees alive had they been
344 exposed to lethal doses. Additionally, we cannot determine what doses the bees had been
345 exposed to since pesticides are metabolized at varying rates (and we do not know the time of
346 exposure), so that the residues we detected represent an unknown proportion of the dose
347 received and actual exposures may have probably been higher. It should also be mentioned
348 that bees are subjected to chronic exposure when foraging on contaminated flowers, and
349 acute LD₅₀s are frequently higher than chronic LD₅₀s, particularly for neonicotinoids (Alkassab
350 and Kirchner, 2016; Rondeau et al., 2014). Thus, the potential risk of chronic exposure to the
351 levels of pesticides detected in the bumblebees cannot be ruled out. Studies where pesticide
352 mixtures are analysed in bees showing health problems or mortality in the field would be of
353 high interest (Kasiotis et al., 2014), since this could provide key information about the hazard
354 posed by specific mixtures and the threshold levels of risk. Nevertheless, such studies are
355 highly challenging to perform in the field due to sampling difficulties, and because the
356 detection of accurate levels at the time of death are problematic since bee samples need to be

357 fresh to avoid degradation of pesticides following exposure to environmental factors and
358 microbial activity (Katagi, 2004; Liu et al., 2011).

359 Our results revealed that 43.3% of bees contained two or more pesticides, suggesting that
360 simultaneous exposure is likely to be encountered regularly in a field realistic scenario.
361 Although contamination with mixtures of pesticides has been detected in flower pollen, bee
362 collected pollen and bees (David et al., 2016; Hladik et al., 2016; Long and Krupke, 2016; Mullin
363 et al., 2010), evaluating the impact of the exposure to such combinations of agrochemicals
364 poses a major challenge and warrants more research. A few laboratory and field studies have
365 explored the impact of simultaneous exposure to different chemicals on bees, some of them
366 reporting detrimental effects of certain combinations (Gill et al., 2012; Iwasa et al., 2004;
367 Johnson et al., 2013; Schmuck et al., 2003; Sgolastra et al., 2016; Thompson and Wilkins,
368 2003). Given the mixtures detected in bees in the present study and in previous research
369 (Hladik et al., 2016; Lambert et al., 2013), the number of possible combinations of pesticides is
370 very high and variable. Therefore, focussing on the most frequent ones when performing
371 assays of bee exposure might be the most sensible approach. Moreover, these scenarios are
372 especially important to consider in cases when two or more pesticides that exhibit synergy are
373 detected simultaneously in bees. For instance, the toxicity of certain insecticides (*e.g.*
374 neonicotinoids and pyrethroids) can be enhanced in the presence of demethylation-inhibiting
375 (DMI) fungicides (*e.g.* epoxiconazole, tebuconazole). In our study, 55.6 % of the bumblebees
376 where neonicotinoid insecticides were detected also contained DMI-fungicides, so exposure to
377 these combinations seems to be likely in the field although it is not known if these
378 concentrations were high enough to induce biological effects. These DMI-fungicides can act as
379 synergists by inhibiting the detoxification system in bees (Iwasa et al., 2004; Johnson et al.,
380 2013; Pilling et al., 1995), and thus the insecticide residues are metabolised or eliminated more
381 slowly. It is also important to remark that this is a limited list of pesticides; due to analytical
382 constraints, insecticides such as pyrethroids, usually detected using gas chromatographic
383 methods and which are known to interact with neonicotinoids and DMI-fungicides, could also
384 be present in these bees.

385 As for the differences in levels of exposure for bees living in farmland or urban habitats, we
386 found that concentrations of pesticides in wild bumblebees foraging in agricultural land were
387 higher than in urban land, as reported for commercial bumblebee colonies in a previous study
388 (David et al., 2016). However, the maximum values for neonicotinoids were recorded in
389 bumblebees collected in urban gardens (*i.e.* 10 ng/g of imidacloprid, 2.35 ng/g of

390 thiamethoxam and 1.4 ng/g of clothianidin), even though these maximum values were high in
391 comparison to the levels detected for these compounds in the rest of the bee specimens
392 collected, so it is possible that these particular bees had been visiting freshly sprayed plants
393 just before they were sampled. The use of imidacloprid, clothianidin and thiamethoxam has
394 been banned since December 2013 on ornamental plants flowering in the year of treatment
395 (as well as on flowering crops) (European Commission, 2013), and so the high levels of
396 imidacloprid in particular are hard to explain. Nonetheless, the result is corroborated by David
397 et al. (2016) who detected high levels (20 ng/g) of imidacloprid in pollen collected by
398 commercial bumblebee colonies placed in urban areas. The imidacloprid may be persisting in
399 urban environments from applications before the ban, or it might still be available in some
400 stores and presumably may be used in gardens for months or even years after the ban.
401 Alternatively, this exposure of bees could originate from other uses of imidacloprid; it is widely
402 used in baits to kill ants and for flea control in dogs and cats. Orally applied imidacloprid in
403 dogs and other mammals is completely eliminated in the urine (70-80%) and faeces (20-30%)
404 in 48 h as the main metabolites 6-chloronicotinic acid and its glycine conjugate together with
405 significant amounts of the parent compound, whereas topical application spreads over the
406 skin for 24 hours and the compound is stored in the oil glands of the skin and slowly shed with
407 hair and sebum (European Food Safety Authority, 2006; Hovda and Hooser, 2002). The
408 environmental impacts of the use of pesticides in ornamental gardens and on pets has been
409 scarcely studied (Brown et al., 2013; Fevery et al., 2016). There is no policing of homeowner
410 use of garden pesticides to ensure that they follow label instructions, and amounts used in
411 gardens are not known. Similarly, we can find no information on the number of dogs and cats
412 treated with imidacloprid as a prophylactic flea treatment, and the environmental fate of such
413 chemicals has not been studied. Urban gardens are an important food source and refuge for
414 bees and other wildlife in cities and towns because they represent the only green space in
415 these large environments, and they can host a great diversity of pollinators and high density of
416 bumblebee nests (Baldock et al., 2015; Fetridge et al., 2008; Goulson et al., 2010), resulting in
417 enhanced pollination services for both urban and nearby agricultural landscapes (Kaluza et al.,
418 2016; Samnegård et al., 2011; Theodorou et al., 2016). If bees are sometimes exposed to high
419 doses of harmful pesticides through forage collected in ornamental gardens, this might be a
420 matter of high ecological concern, meaning that more attention should be paid to this route of
421 contamination for bees.

422 The frequencies of detection and concentrations of agrochemicals in bee tissues decreased
423 significantly in midsummer (July), agreeing with findings reported before (Botías et al., 2015;

424 David et al., 2016) where residue levels decreased in the pollen collected by bees as the season
425 progressed. Midsummer is usually the period for crop harvesting in the studied area, and
426 fewer pesticides are normally applied during this period to crops, so this may partly explain
427 this finding. Concurrently, the decrease in residue levels may be due to a reduction in plant
428 tissue concentrations, and thus on pollen and nectar collected by bees through summer
429 because of plant/soil metabolism, photolysis and increasing temperatures (Bonmatin et al.,
430 2015; Lassalle et al., 2014; Mazellier et al., 2002).

431 *Conclusions and perspectives*

432 The extensive incidence of multiple pesticide residues and the scarcity of scientific literature
433 on the biological consequences of exposure to such combinations on wild bees calls for more
434 attention on regulatory strategies concerning monitoring procedures and registration of
435 agrochemicals as they relate to pollinator protection, since the combined toxicity and
436 synergism of all these chemicals may pose a real threat to the health and survival of managed
437 and wild bees. Thus, investigations on the toxicological effects of field-realistic levels and
438 mixtures are crucial to prevent potential exposure of bees to damaging combinations of
439 agrochemicals. Also, the possible impact of metabolites and of agrochemicals other than
440 insecticides on bees should not be overlooked, as they could have direct or indirect
441 detrimental effects.

442 Understanding the factors involved in the degree of exposure, such as the type of flowers that
443 tend to incorporate more residues or where certain pesticides are more persistent, as well as
444 the morphological and physiological traits of pollinators that makes them more or less
445 susceptible to the exposure, is also crucial to mitigate the damaging effects for the most
446 vulnerable species.

447 Finally, the widespread detection of pesticides in bumblebees foraging in urban areas indicates
448 a pressing need for further research on the prevalence and doses present in ornamental
449 gardens, and on the environmental fate of pesticides upon domestic uses in order to better
450 inform homeowners and garden centers of the potential risk the use of these products poses.
451 Furthermore, surveillance programs on domestic uses would improve the current lack of safety
452 and control in the application of agrochemicals in non-commercial agricultural situations.

453 Our results show evidence that wild bumblebees are frequently exposed to mixtures of
454 agrochemicals when they forage in arable and urban habitats, with peak concentrations
455 decreasing through the season. The effects of exposure to pesticide mixtures in wild bees

456 remain to be determined, but studying the temporal distribution of such combinations in
457 habitats favored by bees is crucial to identify timing and routes of pesticide exposure, which
458 may help us to properly direct our conservation efforts regarding pesticide regulation and bee
459 health protection.

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717 honey bee, *Apis mellifera*, colonies. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health. A* 76, 587–600.
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720 **Tables and Figures**

721 Table 1. Mean (\pm standard deviation) and range of body mass values (mg), and tongue length
722 range (mm) for the five bumblebee species analysed.

BUMBLEBEE SPECIES	BODY MASS (mg)		TONGUE LENGTH RANGE (mm)
	MEAN \pm S.D.	RANGE	(Brodie, 1996; Pry-Jones and Corbet, 2011)
<i>B. hortorum</i>	105 \pm 45	40 - 223	12 - 13.5
<i>B. pascuorum</i>	97 \pm 34	29 - 171	7.6 - 8.6
<i>B. terrestris</i>	142 \pm 46	45 - 236	5.8 - 8.2
<i>B. lapidarius</i>	117 \pm 49	40 - 226	6 - 8.1
<i>B. pratorum</i>	79 \pm 32	21 - 161	6.4 - 7.1

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738 Table 2. Frequencies of detection (%), maximum concentrations (Max), average (Avg) and
739 median values (Mdn)(ng/g) of neonicotinoid insecticides and fungicides detected in wild
740 bumblebees. The analytical methods do not allow us to differentiate what fraction of the
741 pesticide was on the surface (contact toxicity) or inside the bumblebee (oral) since all
742 specimens were individually processed as whole samples. Therefore, LD₅₀ values of contact (C)
743 and/or oral (O) toxicity for honeybees (hb) or bumblebees (bb), according to availability of
744 data (Sánchez-Bayo and Goka, 2014), are reported for each of the pesticides that were
745 detected in wild bumblebees.

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		CONCENTRATIONS (ng/g)												
		LATE SPRING (27/4/14 - 14/5/14)				EARLY SUMMER (5/6/14 - 23/6/14)				MIDSUMMER (15/7/14 - 2/8/14)				
		ARABLE (N=25)		URBAN (N=25)		ARABLE (N=25)		URBAN (N=25)		ARABLE (N=25)		URBAN (N=25)		
		Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	Freq. %	Avg. Mdn	
Contact (C) and/or oral (O) LD50s reported for bumblebees (bb) or honeybees (hb)														
Neonicotinoid insecticides														
Thiamethoxam	C = 25 ng/hb; O = 5 ng/hb	8%	<0.90	12%	<0.90	<0.30	<0.30	0%	16%	2.35	<0.30	<0.30	0%	0%
Clothianidin	C = 16 ng/bb	4%	<1.4	0%				0%	4%	1.4	<0.48	<0.48	0%	0%
Imidacloprid	C = 20 ng/bb; O = 27 ng/bb	0%		16%	<2.2	<0.72	<0.72	0%	24%	10	<0.72	<0.72	4%	<2.2
Thiacloprid	C = 36,000 ng/hb; O = 17,000 ng/bb	0%		0%				0%	12%	1.17	<0.07	<0.02	0%	0%
Acetamiprid	C = 100,000 ng/hb; O = 22,000 ng/bb	0%		0%				0%	4%	0.17	<0.01	<0.01	0%	0%
MBC-Fungicide														
Carbendazim	C => 50,000 ng/hb	8%	1.2	<0.14	<0.05	28.8	1.49	<0.05	8%	1.2	<0.14	<0.05	12%	4.37
SDHI-Fungicides														
Carboxin		0%		0%				0%	0%				0%	
Boscalid	C => 200,000 ng/hb; O = 166,000 ng/hb	76%	31.7	7.03	6.2	13.4	1.35	<0.24	44%	5.94	<0.05	<0.05	36%	54.4
Amine fungicide														
Spiroxamine	C = 4,200 ng/hb; O = 92,000 ng/hb	4%	3.8	0.15	<0.05	0%		0%	96%	37.7	6.51	2.91	0%	12%
DMI fungicides														
Triticonazole		0%		0%				0%	0%				0%	
Epoxiconazole	C => 100,000 ng/hb	48%	6.07	1.03	<0.96	0%		0%	4%	<2.9	<0.96	<0.96	0%	0%
Tebuconazole	C => 200,000 ng/hb; O = 83,000 ng/hb	12%	1.7	<0.12	<0.12	8%	<0.36	<0.12	88%	11.7	2.91	1.59	28%	1.5
Flusilazole		0%		0%				0%	0%				0%	
Prochloraz	C => 50,000 ng/hb; O = 60,000 ng/hb	0%		0%				0%	4%	<0.90	<0.30	<0.30	0%	0%
Metconazole	C => 100,000 ng/hb; O = 80,000 ng/hb	20%	<0.72	<0.24	<0.24	8%	4	<0.24	0%	<0.90	<0.30	<0.24	4%	2.58
QoI-fungicides														
Pyraclostrobin	C => 100,000 ng/hb; O = 73,000 ng/hb	4%	<0.72	<0.24	<0.24	0%		0%	0%				0%	
Trifloxystrobin	C => 200,000 ng/hb; O = 200,000 ng/hb	4%	2.74	0.11	<0.01	4%	2.74	0.11	12%	<0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0%	0%
Fluoxastrobin	C => 200,000 ng/hb; O = 843,000 ng/hb	12%	<0.72	<0.24	<0.24	4%	<0.72	<0.24	4%	<0.72	<0.24	<0.24	0%	0%
Synergist														
Piperonyl butoxide		0%		0%				0%	0%				0%	

Figure 1. Location of sites in East Sussex (UK), where wild bumblebees were collected from farmland sites (circles) and urban sites (squares). The sites selected to collect bees in agricultural land consisted of arable fields within mixed farms, where the predominant crops were oilseed rape, winter wheat and spring barley, and part of the land was pasture. The urban sampling sites consisted of ornamental public gardens and parks surrounded by houses that had private gardens in most cases.

Figure 2. Sum of total concentrations of neonicotinoid insecticides and fungicides detected in 5 different species of wild bumblebees collected in arable (A) and urban (U) sites in three sampling periods (May, June and July). Concentrations reported refer to the amount of active substance (ng) detected per bumblebee body weight (g).

Figure 3. Frequencies of detection (%) of pesticide residues in wild bumblebees collected in arable and urban habitats in May, June and July.

Supplementary Information

- Experimental procedures.

Quality control

In order to guarantee the lack of contamination during the preparation of samples and the absence of carryover in the UHPLC system, every batch of samples injected included a workup sample at the beginning of the HPLC-MS/MS run and solvent samples between batches. The pesticides detected were identified after the comparison of multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transition ratios in pure standards and samples. Instrumental performance and sensitivity changes were assessed by injecting quality control samples (standard solutions) every 10 samples, and the standard calibration mixture at the beginning and the end of all sample batches.

- Tables and Figures

Table S1. Sampling locations and GPS coordinates of the urban sites where wild bumblebees samples were collected, surveying circa 100 m radius around these points. Bumblebees collected in farmland were sampled on private land for which research permission was granted by the owners. Private landowners who granted access in this study wish to remain anonymous and specific GPS coordinates cannot be provided as part of that confidentiality.

Sampling site	Latitude	Longitude	Location	Distance to nearest arable crop
URBAN 1	50°49'25.11" N	0°18'45.34" W	Lancing	1,822 m
URBAN 2	50°50'7.71" N	0°15'30.99" W	Shoreham-by-Sea	1,397 m
URBAN 3	50°50'14.30" N	0°12'53.47" W	Portsmouth	2,295 m
URBAN 4	50°50'41.53" N	0°10'28.52" W	Hove	1,591 m
URBAN 5	50°50'12.61" N	0°7'12.32" W	Brighton	2,435 m

Tables S2a-S2c. Concentrations (ng/g bee body weight) of neonicotinoid insecticides and fungicides detected in all the wild bumblebee specimens collected in this study in arable and urban habitats during three sampling periods (late spring: 27/04/14 – 14/05/14 - Table S2a; early summer: 5/06/14 – 23/06/14 - Table S2b; and midsummer: 15/07/14 – 2/08/14 - Table S2c). The residues that were found at detectable levels are highlighted in bold. Abbreviations: TMX = thiamethoxam, CLO = clothianidin, IMC = imidacloprid, ACT = acetamiprid, THC = thiacloprid.

Table S3. Estimated usage data in 2014 (FERA, 2015) for the pesticides analysed. Total arable land area in the UK in 2014 was 6,233,500 Ha (data provided by FAOSTAT: <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RL>).

*Usage data from 2013, no data available for this formulation in 2014

PESTICIDES	FORMULATION	AREA TREATED (Ha)	WEIGHT OF A.S. APPLIED (Kg)
Neonicotinoid insecticides			
Thiamethoxam	Thiamethoxam	43,255	2,595
	Thiamethoxam/Fluodioxonil/Metalaxyl-M	311,897	8,744
Clothianidin	Clothianidin	68,034	5,941
	Clothianidin/Prothioconazole	769,688	81,514
	Clothianidin/Beta-cyfluthrin	223,664	8,398
Imidacloprid	Imidacloprid/Beta-cyfluthrin	1,904	83
Thiacloprid	Thiacloprid	30,453	2,855
Acetamiprid	Acetamiprid	2,777	ND
MBC-Fungicide			
Carbendazim	Carbendazim	152,497	33,193
	Carbendazim/Flusilazole	128,961	21,231
SDHI-Fungicides			
Carboxin	Carboxin/Thiram	56,780*	ND
Boscalid	Boscalid	724,496	130,000
Amine fungicide			
Spiroxamine	Spiroxamine	711,931	132,000
DMI fungicides			
Triticonazole	Triticonazole/Prochloraz	567,042	16,694
Epoxiconazole	Epoxiconazole	3,783,354	227,000
Tebuconazole	Tebuconazole	3,586,689	385,000
Flusilazole	Flusilazole	108,920	11,965
	Flusilazole/Carbendazim	128,961	21,231
Prochloraz	Prochloraz	684,227	130,000
Metconazole	Metconazole	233,499	10,923
	Metconazole/Boscalid	75,629	11,031
	Metconazole/Epoxiconazole	512,811	35,758
	Metconazole/Fluxapyroxad	158,849	16,654
	Metconazole/Mepiquat chloride	53,114	11,696
QoI-fungicides			
Pyraclostrobin	Pyraclostrobin	988,505	74,000
Trifloxystrobin	Trifloxystrobin/Cyproconazole	135,476	24,134
	Trifloxystrobin/Fluoxastrobin/Prothioconazole	200,158	27,267
	Trifloxystrobin/Prothioconazole	212,054	31,955
Fluoxastrobin	Fluoxastrobin/Bixaflen/Prothioconazole	97,996	23,132
	Fluoxastrobin/Prothioconazole	262,384	40,059
	Fluoxastrobin/Prothioconazole/Trifloxystrobin	200,158	27,267
Synergist			
Piperonyl butoxide		ND	ND

Table S4. Method detection limits (MDL) and method quantification limits (MQL) of neonicotinoid and fungicide calculated from spiked bumblebee samples.

	MDL ng/g <i>bee body weight</i>	MQL ng/g <i>bee body weight</i>
Thiamethoxam	0.30	0.90
Clothianidin	0.48	1.4
Imidacloprid	0.72	2.2
Acetamiprid	0.01	0.04
Thiacloprid	0.02	0.07
Carbendazim	0.05	0.14
Carboxin	0.24	0.72
Spiroxamine	0.05	0.14
Triticonazole	0.48	1.4
Epoxiconazole	0.96	2.9
Boscalid	0.24	0.72
Tebuconazole	0.12	0.36
Flusilazole	0.12	0.36
Prochloraz	0.30	0.90
Metconazole	0.24	0.72
Fluoxastrobin	0.24	0.72
Pyraclostrobin	0.24	0.72
Trifloxystrobin	0.01	0.04
Piperonyl butoxide	0.24	0.72